

Analysis of The Influence of Brand Awareness, Brand Image and Price on Purchasing Decisions for Samase Products in Jakarta

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ABSTRACT: The demand for Muslim clothing is increasing rapidly. This is happening because of the increasing population of Muslims every year, so fashion companies must be able to meet consumer needs. Samase, as a fashion company, has a strong commitment to fulfilling consumer rights, especially in meeting the demands of Muslim consumers. Evidence of this commitment can be seen from the number of agents/distributors spread across the DKI Jakarta area. This study uses a quantitative approach with the aim of proving and analyzing the effect of brand awareness, brand image, and price on purchasing decisions for Samase products in Jakarta. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, with a total sample of 100 respondents. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive analysis techniques and inferential analysis using the SmartPLS application (V.3.29). The results of this study indicate that: (1) Brand awareness has a positive and significant impact on purchasing decisions, with a path effect of 0.515. (2) Brand image also has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions, with a path effect of 0.515. 0.286. (3) In addition, price also influences purchasing decisions positively and significantly, with a path effect of 0.141. Overall, brand awareness, brand image, and price together contributed 0.733 (73.3%) to purchasing decisions, while the remaining 0.267 (26.7%) was influenced by other factors outside this research model.

KEYWORDS: brand awareness; brand image; price; purchase decision.

INTRODUCTION

Background

The economic condition of a country can be influenced by several factors, one of which is the population size. According to Setyaningsih (2021), considering the significant potential of the Muslim population in Indonesia, the country has the opportunity to become a major player in the global halal economy. However, achieving this requires serious efforts in the development of the halal industry. The government has taken steps to realize this by implementing Government Regulation No. 39 of 2021 on the implementation of halal product guarantees. The aim of this measure is to streamline the process of obtaining halal certificates, thereby supporting the growth of SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) and halal tourism (Setyaningsih, 2021). This initiative cannot succeed without the support of the population in Indonesia. The population of Indonesia based on religious affiliation is presented in the following figure:

Figure 1. Total Population by Religion Source: <https://databoks.katadata.co.id/>

Samase is a quite popular Muslim fashion and already has its own market position. This is evident from the following picture:

Figure 2. Search Results for Muslim Clothing Brands on Google Source: google.com

From the above picture, it is evident that simply typing 'men's Muslim clothing brand' on Google or social media with that keyword results in the brand 'samase' being mentioned as the first result on the website list. mentions the brand "samase." In this case, the brand "samase" is positioned first when reviewed by several websites. The market response indicates that the 'samase' brand is making efforts to endure amidst business competition. However, let's examine the Top Brand Index in the following picture:

TOP BRAND INDEX FASE 2 2022

TOP BRAND INDEX FASE 2 2021

BUSANA MUSLIM			BAJU KOKO			BUSANA MUSLIM			BAJU KOKO		
BRAND	TBI 2022		BRAND	TBI 2022		BRAND	TBI 2021		BRAND	TBI 2021	
Rabbani	22.3%	TOP	Rabbani	25.3%	TOP	Rabbani	22.2%	TOP	Rabbani	26.8%	TOP
Zoya	20.5%	TOP	Atlas	17.7%	TOP	Zoya	21.3%	TOP	Atlas	18.7%	TOP
Almadani	14.5%	TOP	Zoya	15.9%	TOP	Almadani	13.6%	TOP	Al Mia	15.5%	TOP
Azka	10.9%		Dannis	15.6%		Azka	10.4%		Dannis	14.8%	
Attena	8.2%		Al Mia	13.2%		Attena	7.5%		Zoya	7.3%	
* Kategori online dan offline			* Kategori online dan offline			* Kategori online dan offline			* Kategori online dan offline		

Figure 3. Top Brand Index Phase 2
Data Source: <https://www.topbrand-award.com/>

In the above image, it is clear that Samase has not entered the Top Brand Index in both the Muslim fashion and Koko shirt categories. Therefore, this serves as a trigger for the company to reconsider the factors that can influence Samase's brand to become a top brand. One of the efforts is to enhance the brand image, brand awareness, and review the appropriate pricing to compete in the sales of this Samase brand with the aim of increasing consumer purchase decisions. Strengthening the general and specific phenomena explained, there are inconsistencies in some previous studies, which serve as a strong rationale for conducting this research. According to Rafidah, Kurniawan, Zia (2016), in their study, they stated that brand awareness has a positive and significant impact on purchase decisions. In contrast, Amelfdi, F. J., & Ardyan, E. (2020), based on their research, found that

brand awareness individually does not significantly affect purchase decisions. Findings from the study conducted by Shafitri, R. (2022) indicate that brand image has a positive and significant impact on purchase decisions. This differs from the results of the research conducted by Saifuddin & Rahmayanti, N. M. (2021), which explains that brand image does not significantly affect purchase decisions. Finally, the results of the research conducted by Tritama, Nobelson Syarief, Pusporini (2021) show that price has a positive and significant impact on purchase decisions. This is in contrast to the research by Tumangger, Y., Daulay, A., & Surbakti, S. B. (2022), which found that price does not significantly influence purchase decisions.

Problem Formulation

Based on the background mentioned, the problem formulation for this research can be obtained as follows:

1. Does brand awareness influence the purchasing decisions of Samase products in Jakarta?
2. Does brand image influence the purchasing decisions of Samase products in Jakarta?
3. Does pricing influence the purchasing decisions of Samase products in Jakarta?

RESEARCH METHOD

This research involves two types of variables: independent variables (brand awareness, brand image, and pricing) and dependent variables (purchase decisions). The measurement of purchase decisions is conducted using indicators such as product selection, brand selection, distributor/agent selection, purchase timing, and purchase quantity. Meanwhile, brand awareness (X1) is measured through indicators of recall, recognition, and purchase. Brand image (X2) is measured through indicators of corporate image, user image, and product image. Pricing (X3) is measured through indicators of price affordability, price-quality suitability, and price competitiveness and suitability with benefits. The population of this research comprises Samase consumers in Jakarta who have either purchased or are currently using Samase products. Sample selection is performed using purposive sampling techniques, resulting in 100 samples based on the calculation using the Lemeshow formula. Data for this research is collected using G-Form questionnaires as the primary data source. The questionnaire covers variables such as brand awareness, brand image, pricing, and purchase decisions, utilizing a Likert scale for data measurement. The analysis employed includes descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. The analysis tool to be used is Partial Least Squares (PLS) with SmartPLS 3.29 software

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Description of Respondent Data (Respondent Characteristics)

In this study, 100 respondents are described based on gender, age, occupation, income, and domicile/activities. The majority of respondents are described as follows:

1. Based on gender, there are 87 male respondents (87%) and 13 female respondents (13%). The majority of respondents are male, consistent with Dihni's research (2022), which states that the fashion spending budget for men tends to be higher than for women.
2. Based on age, there are 9 respondents (9%) in the age range of 17-21 years, 31 respondents (31%) in the age range of 22-31 years, 18 respondents (18%) in the age range of 27-31 years, and 42 respondents (42%) above 31 years. The majority of respondents are above 31 years old, belonging to the millennial "Y" generation, known for their consumer behavior (Sugeng Riyanto, 2021).
3. Based on occupation: there are 44 respondents (44%) working as private employees, 17 respondents (17%) as entrepreneurial employees, 12 respondents (12%) as students, 5 respondents (5%) as civil servants, 2 respondents (2%) as students, and 20 respondents (20%) in other occupations. The majority of respondents are private employees, indicating that occupation influences consumer purchasing power (Simamora, cited in Anastasia, 2017).
4. Based on income, there are 41 respondents (41%) with income above Rp5,000,000, 25 respondents (25%) with income between Rp3,000,000 and Rp5,000,000, 15 respondents (15%) with income between Rp1,000,000 and Rp3,000,000, 7 respondents (7%) with income between Rp500,000 and Rp1,000,000, and 12 respondents (12%) with income below Rp500,000. The majority of respondents have income above Rp5,000,000, aligning with higher fashion spending budgets for men (Dihni, 2022).
5. Based on domicile/activities, there are 57 respondents (57%) from North Jakarta, 25 respondents (25%) from South Jakarta, 11 respondents (11%) from East Jakarta, 4 respondents (4%) from Central Jakarta, and 3 respondents (3%) from West Jakarta.

The majority of respondents come from North Jakarta, with a small portion from South Jakarta and a smaller number in other regions.

The characteristics of the respondents in this study are predominantly male, aged above 31 years, employed as private workers, with an income above Rp5,000,000, and engaged in activities in the North Jakarta area.

Descriptive Analysis

The method of descriptive analysis is used in this research to process data from the questionnaires filled out by respondents. Subsequently, an analysis will be conducted in the form of interpretation of the indices to provide an overview of respondents' perceptions of the variables in this study. It can be interpreted with several categories: 0%–20% (very low), 21%–40% (low), 41%–60% (medium/moderately high), 61%–80% (high), 81%–100% (very high), through 12 statements for purchase decision variables, 6 statements for brand awareness, 7 statements for brand image, and 8 statements for pricing. Data regarding response index scores to purchase decision variables have been analyzed and presented:

Table 1. Index of Respondents' Responses to Purchasing Decisions

Purchase Decision	1		2		3		4		5		Index
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
KP1	2	2%	5	5%	8	8,00%	46	46,00%	39	39,00%	65,00%
KP2	0	0%	2	2%	6	6,00%	56	56,00%	36	36,00%	65,20%
KP3	2	2%	14	14%	18	18,00%	45	45,00%	21	21,00%	55,80%
KP4	1	1%	1	1%	5	5,00%	47	47,00%	46	46,00%	68,20%
KP5	1	1%	7	7%	12	12,00%	45	45,00%	35	35,00%	62,20%
KP6	13	13%	25	25%	22	22,00%	25	25,00%	15	15,00%	53,80%
KP7	8	8%	6	6%	14	14,00%	29	29,00%	43	43,00%	66,60%
KP8	1	1%	4	4%	7	7,00%	50	50,00%	38	38,00%	65,00%
KP9	6	6%	15	15%	14	14,00%	36	36,00%	29	29,00%	59,40%
KP10	3	3%	3	3%	7	7,00%	33	33,00%	54	54,00%	69,40%
KP11	5	5%	25	25%	26	26,00%	22	22,00%	22	22,00%	51,20%
KP12	1	1%	8	8%	13	13,00%	47	47,00%	31	31,00%	60,80%
Average total index											61,88%

Source table: Data processed

The results of the analysis indicate that all statements in Table 1 regarding the purchase decision variable are classified as "high." Statement KP10 received the highest approval (69.40%) with 36 respondents "agreeing" to the statement "Buying Samase products when having enough money." Statement KP11 had the lowest approval (51.20%) with 22 respondents agreeing to the statement "Buying Samase products more than one to meet needs." The average index of the purchase decision variable is 61.88%, indicating that the majority of respondents agree with the choices of Samase products, brands, distributors/agents, timing, and quantity of purchases. This means that the statements representing each indicator describing the purchase decision variable can explain the variable effectively.

Table 2. Respondent Response Index on Brand awareness

Brand Awareness	1		2		3		4		5		Index
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
BA1	0	0%	3	3%	2	2,00%	43	43,00%	52	52,00%	68,80%
BA2	0	0%	2	2%	6	6,00%	41	41,00%	51	51,00%	68,20%
BA3	1	1%	4	4%	9	9,00%	37	37,00%	49	49,00%	66,80%

BA4	2	2%	3	3%	11	11,00%	39	39,00%	45	45,00%	66,40%
BA5	3	3%	3	3%	15	15,00%	43	43,00%	36	36,00%	64,20%
BA6	1	1%	10	10%	16	16,00%	45	45,00%	28	28,00%	58,80%
Average total index											65,53%

Source of table: Data Processed

The analysis results show that all indicators of brand awareness variable statement items has a "high" index value (61% - 80%). Statement BA1 received highest approval value (68.80%) was obtained with 52 respondents "strongly agreeing" with the statement "The product falls into the category of contemporary Muslim fashion brands and is always up to date yet remains modest." Statement BA6 had the lowest score (58.80%) and is categorized as "moderate" (41% – 60%) for the statement "Making the product I like as the first choice among purchases in the Muslim fashion brand category." The average brand awareness index is 65.53%, indicating that the majority of respondents agree with statements related to brand awareness. This means that the statements representing each indicator describing the brand awareness variable can effectively explain the variable.

Table 3. Respondent Response Index on Brand image

Brand Image	1		2		3		4		5		Index
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
BI1	1	1%	1	1%	10	10,00%	45	45,00%	43	43,00%	66,60%
BI2	1	1%	1	1%	6	6,00%	46	46,00%	46	46,00%	68,00%
BI3	0	0%	3	3%	10	10,00%	43	43,00%	44	44,00%	65,60%
BI4	2	2%	4	4%	8	8,00%	40	40,00%	46	46,00%	66,80%
BI5	2	2%	2	2%	7	7,00%	47	47,00%	42	42,00%	67,00%
BI6	0	0%	4	4%	5	5,00%	41	41,00%	50	50,00%	67,40%
BI7	1	1%	0	0%	7	7,00%	44	44,00%	48	48,00%	68,60%
Ra Average total index											67,14%

Source of table: Data Processed

The analysis results indicate that almost all statements regarding the brand image variable have "high" index values according to the criteria for interpreting questionnaire scores. Statement BI7 received the highest approval (68.60%) with 48 respondents "strongly agreeing" with the statement "The product design is very attractive." Statement BI3 had the lowest score (65.60%) and is categorized as "high" for the statement "Wearing the product can make the wearer appear lively in an Islamic atmosphere yet still modern." The average brand image index is 67.14%, indicating that the majority of respondents agree with statements related to brand image. This means that the statements representing each indicator describing the brand image variable can effectively explain the variable.

Table 4. Index of Respondents' Responses to Price

Price	1		2		3		4		5		Index
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
H1	3	3%	11	11%	34	34,00%	35	35,00%	17	17,00%	53,40%
H2	0	0%	2	2%	25	25,00%	53	53,00%	20	20,00%	58,20%
H3	0	0%	1	1%	14	14,00%	47	47,00%	38	38,00%	64,40%
H4	1	1%	3	3%	18	18,00%	46	46,00%	32	32,00%	62,00%
H5	0	0%	0	0%	15	15,00%	48	48,00%	37	37,00%	64,40%
H6	2	2%	8	8%	32	32,00%	39	39,00%	19	19,00%	55,00%

H7	0	0%	4	4%	16	16,00%	45	45,00%	35	35,00%	62,20%
H8	0	0%	4	4%	34	34,00%	38	38,00%	24	24,00%	56,40%
Average total index										59,50%	

Source table: Data Processed

The analysis indicates that all statements regarding the price variable fall into the "moderate" category. Statement H3 obtained the highest score (64.40%) with 47 respondents "agreeing" with the statement "The offered price is in line with the product quality." Statement H1 had the lowest score (53.40%) but is still categorized as "moderate"; the statement is "The price of the product is affordable." The average price index is 59.50%, indicating a satisfactory explanation of the price variable.

Inferential Data Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

The data analysis methods applied in this study include validity testing, reliability testing, and hypothesis testing. SmartPLS 3.29 software is utilized as the tool for conducting these tests.

Table 5. Output of loading factor values

	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Brand awareness	0.684	0.883	0.915
Brand image	0.671	0.917	0.934
Price	0.651	0.925	0.937
Purchase decision	0.550	0.861	0.894

Source table: SmartPLS 3.29 output results

In Table 5, based on the discriminant validity test, convergent validity is measured through the calculation of loading factors for each statement and loading factors on the variables of brand awareness, brand image, price, and purchase decision. From these results, it can be concluded that each variable has a loading factor (AVE) with a value exceeding 0.50. Thus, based on these calculations, all indicators can be considered valid as they meet the established criteria. The results of the reliability test for all variables show a high level of reliability, based on Ghozali's research (2014, p. 39), where all variables have Cronbach's alpha values exceeding 0.7. With this, the research instrument can be deemed valid and reliable. After all items and variables are declared valid and reliable, the next step is to conduct the Q-Square (Q2) and R-Square (R2) tests. The Q2 value serves to determine the extent to which the model in this study represents the population. After reviewing the validity and reliability results of all items and variables, it can be concluded that this research instrument has high validity and reliability. The next stage is to conduct the Q-Square (Q2) and R-Square (R2) tests to measure how well the research model can represent the studied population. Based on the test results, a Q-Square (Q2) value of 0.386 is obtained, indicating that the model has predictive relevance. Furthermore, the R2 value is used to measure the influence of brand awareness, brand image, and price on purchase decisions. The R Square (R2) value for the purchase decision variable is 0.733 or 73.3%. This means that the variables of brand awareness, brand image, and price can explain 73.3% of the contribution to the influence on purchase decisions. However, there is approximately 26.7% of the influence contribution to purchase decisions that can be attributed to factors other than brand awareness, brand image, and price. Subsequently, this study conducted hypothesis testing using the t-test method. The t-test or partial test is used to evaluate whether there is a significant influence between brand awareness (X1), brand image (X2), and price (X3) on purchase decisions (Y). The results of the data analysis using the significance test (t-test) yield the following findings:

Table 6: Results of the t-test

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>T Statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P Values</i>
<i>Brand awareness</i> -> Purchase Decision	0.515	4.341	0.000
<i>Brand image</i> -> Purchase Decision	0.286	2.452	0.015
<i>Price</i> -> Purchase Decision	0.141	2.036	0.042

Source table: SmartPLS 3.29 *output* results

Based on Table 6, it can be observed that the calculation results show that the brand awareness variable (X1) has a positive original sample (os) value of 0.515. This is supported by comparing the calculated t-value (4.341) with the t-table value (1.98498), and a significance value (P Values) of 0.000, which is < 0.05. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted, while the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected. This result indicates that the brand awareness variable has a positive and significant influence on purchase decisions. From this finding, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant influence between the brand awareness variable and purchase decisions. According to Table 6, it is also evident that the calculation results show that the brand image variable (X2) has a positive original sample (os) value of 0.286. From the data processing outcome, the calculated t-value (2.452) is greater than the t-table value (1.98498), and the significance value (P Values) is 0.015, which is < 0.05. Therefore, the brand image variable has a positive and significant influence on purchase decisions. This supports the research hypothesis stating that brand image has an impact on purchase decisions. Furthermore, based on Table 6, it can be seen that the calculation results show that the price variable (X3) yields a positive original sample (os) value of 0.141. From the data processing findings, the calculated t-value (2.036) is greater than the t-table value (1.98498), and the significance value (P Values) is 0.042, which is not greater than 0.05. Therefore, the price variable has a positive and significant impact on purchase decisions. This supports the research hypothesis stating that price has an impact on purchase decisions.

DISCUSSION

The analysis results indicate that brand awareness has a positive and significant impact on purchase decisions (effect 0.515). Respondents indicate that the factor influencing the purchase decision of Samase products in Jakarta is "fashion products that support worship while maintaining practicality." Samase needs to maintain brand awareness (through continuous branding) with strategies such as appealing logos and taglines, active presence on social media, and the use of popular influencers. Other research by Rafidah, Kurniawan, and Zia (2016) supports these findings.

The analysis also shows that brand image has a positive and significant impact on purchase decisions (effect 0.286). What influences the purchase decision of Samase in Jakarta is "products that create an impression of living in an Islamic atmosphere yet still appearing modern." Samase needs to maintain a good image (through continuous branding) through credibility in production, product innovation, understanding consumer needs, attractive product design, and consistent brand communication. Other research by Tumangger, Daulay, and Surbakti (2022) supports these findings

The price variable also has a positive and significant impact on purchase decisions (effect 0.141). The price that aligns with the benefits and consumers' purchasing power, as well as attractive price competitiveness, influences the purchase decision of Samase. Samase needs to consider the affordability of prices, alignment with quality and benefits, as well as good after-sales service. Other research by Nasution (2020) supports these findings.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The contribution of brand awareness to the improvement of Samase product purchase decisions is significant or quite substantial. This indicates that consumers of Samase products pay attention to a good level of brand awareness, including recall, recognition, and positive purchasing decisions when making purchase decisions. Specifically, consumers consider purchasing Samase products when they recognize the name, logo, tagline, and brand embedded in their minds, perceiving Samase as a contemporary and up-to-date Muslim fashion brand while remaining modest. The findings of this research align with the hypotheses formulated, namely that brand awareness influences the purchase decisions of Samase products in Jakarta. The research findings support the previously stated hypotheses, indicating the impact of brand awareness on Samase product purchase decisions in Jakarta.

The contribution of brand image to the improvement of Samase product purchase decisions is also significant or quite substantial. This shows that Samase product consumers consider a good corporate image, user image, and product image when making purchase decisions. Consumers contemplate buying Samase products when they see attractive product designs that align with contemporary trends but still adhere to Islamic rules. The results of this research are consistent with the hypotheses outlined, namely that brand image influences the purchase decisions of Samase products in Jakarta.

The contribution of price to the improvement of Samase product purchase decisions is also significant or quite substantial. This indicates that consumers of Samase products pay attention to affordable pricing, alignment of price with product quality, price competitiveness, and alignment of price with the benefits provided when making purchase decisions. In particular, consumers consider buying Samase products when the offered price aligns with the product's quality. The outcomes of this research are in line with the proposed hypotheses, stating that price has an impact on Samase product purchase decisions in Jakarta.

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Cite this Article: Rifqi Febriansyah, Heni Nastiti (2024). Analysis of The Influence of Brand Awareness, Brand Image and Price on Purchasing Decisions for Samase Products in Jakarta. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(1), 12-19